

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL PREDICTORS OF PASSION FOR RELIGION: THE ROLE OF SENSATION SEEKING, DEVIANT ASSOCIATION AND NEED FOR CLOSURE

Hayat Muhammad^{*1}, Maria Wali², Syeda Bakhtawar Gillani³, Maliha Bukhari⁴, Shakir Ullah⁵

^{*1}PhD, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology, University of Peshawar, KP, Pakistan, ,

^{2,3,4}BS student, Department of Psychology, University of Peshawar, KP, Pakistan

⁵PhD Scholar, Department of Psychology, University of Haripur

^{*1}hayat_bangash@hotmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/>

Keywords

Religiosity, deviant association, need for closure, sensation seeking, passion for religion, and societal influence.

Article History

Received: 25 May, 2025

Accepted: 07 August, 2025

Published: 25 August, 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Hayat Muhammad

Abstract

Religion can serve as a stabilizing and energizing factor in a world where people frequently cope with risks, uncertainty, and the pull of various social influences. With a primary focus on sensation seeking, the need for closure, and deviant association, this study attempted to examine how specific psychological characteristics and social settings impact religious dedication. 354 people participated in the study, including drug users (13.8%), university students (24.9%), inmates (33.1%), and internet respondents (28.2%). They filled out validated scales that assessed the variables under investigation. The analysis of the study indicated that while deviant association ($\beta = -.34, p < .001$) was a negative predictor of passion for religion, sensation seeking ($\beta = .431, p < .001$) and the need for closure ($\beta = .206, p < .001$) were significantly positive predictors. Simply stated, it appears that religion may appeal to sensation seekers because of its captivating rituals and stimulating practices. It may also offer consolation to those who are in high need of closure by providing them with certainty and structure. However, members of deviant peer groups were less likely to be religiously passionate, perhaps as a result of their promotion of opposing worldviews that weaken religious commitment. Overall, the study findings indicate that people's adherence to religion is influenced by both psychological needs and social surroundings. Although religion can be viewed as a source of stability and meaning, external factors might minimize its impact.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most enduring and significant institutions in human history has always been religion. It influences moral behavior, shapes personal beliefs, and gives people purpose in the midst of ambiguity or difficulty. Researchers in the fields of psychology, sociology, and anthropology have attempted to understand why people become so passionate about religion over the years. While some have emphasized personality-based approaches, others have focused on

structural theories of socialization. However, in more recent years, the focus of research has switched to examining the ways in which social settings and psychological characteristics combine to influence religious commitment. This study expands on this viewpoint by examining the relationship between passion for religion and three key factors: sensory seeking, deviant association, and need for closure.

Sensation seeking, defined as the tendency to pursue novel, intricate, and intense experiences despite potential risks (Zuckerman, 1994), has primarily been examined in relation to risk-taking behaviors such as substance abuse, gambling, and delinquency. However, its relationship to religion is less obvious. In fact, one study at the European Psychiatric Conference examined this relationship using Allport's Religious Orientation Scale and Zuckerman's Sensation Seeking Scale (Hatam, Baranovich, & Fard, 2017). Although the limitation of research in this area still exists, some studies indicate that individuals who are highly sensation seekers might not stick too much with traditional or very intrinsic forms of religiosity. However, other forms of religious expression, such as ritual activities or charismatic worship, can be very emotional and dramatic, which may actually attract sensation seekers (Zinnbauer & Pargament, 2005). Therefore, even though sensation seeking is frequently associated with dangerous actions, it may also contribute to religious passion when religion provides novelty, excitement, or even just a sense of belongingness.

Deviant association, a sociology term used that describe a person's affiliation with individuals or groups that are thought to violate social standards or expectations. The person may start exhibiting aberrant attitudes, behaviour, and beliefs as a result of this relationship. Social learning theory suggests that individuals internalize behaviors, values, and beliefs through exposure to their social environment, whether close-knit or peripheral (Akers, 1998). People's thoughts and feelings about religion can be influenced by even remote or indirect ties to religious communities. However, deviant affiliations, such as belonging to stigmatized groups like addicts or convicts, might also encourage people to turn to religion as a means of coping with life, finding structure, or finding salvation. Research on people who are imprisoned, for example, has demonstrated that religious participation can provide purpose, aid in adjustment, and even lessen disciplinary issues (Clear & Sumter, 2002; Clear et al., 2000). Similarly, studies on desistance show that religion can give marginalized individuals an opportunity to reconstruct their identities and reestablish connections with society (Maruna, 2001). These findings indicate that, whether through distant or

deviant associations, social exposure can cultivate passion for religion.

The concept extensively studied by Kruglanski and colleagues is the need for closure, which specifies an individual's motivation to reach a quick and definite answer to a question, thus avoiding ambiguity and uncertainty. It is not a weakness, but rather a proclivity to seek structure and closure in situations, especially when confronted with ambiguity or complexity. Research indicates that individuals with a high need for closure are more attracted to structured belief systems, including fundamentalist religious ideologies, because they offer definitive answers and reduce uncertainty (Roets & Van Hiel, 2011). A recent study further demonstrated that the need for closure strengthens identity fusion with religious groups, mediated by religious ideology, thereby consolidating individuals' commitment to religion (Smeekes et al., 2025). According to empirical research, those who have a greater need for closure tend to be more authoritarian, dogmatic, and devoted to strict beliefs (Brandt et al., 2014). This essentially implies that for those who have a strong desire to overcome uncertainty in their lives, religion can serve as an emotional and cognitive anchor. Although the need for closure, social exposure, and sensation seeking have all been examined in connection with religion separately, there hasn't been much study that combines them into a single framework. Previous research has demonstrated that sensation seeking is typically associated with risky behaviors and, in certain situations, with religious orientation (Zuckerman, 1994; Hatam, Baranovich, & Fard, 2017).

Social associations are also important since religious identity can be shaped by social learning from both close and distant relationships (Akers, 1998). This is particularly true for marginalized populations like prisoners, for whom religion helps in rehabilitation and coping (Clear & Sumter, 2002). Conversely, the need for closure has been repeatedly associated with dogmatism and a greater inclination toward organized belief systems, such as religious fundamentalism (Kruglanski & Webster, 1996; Roets & Van Hiel, 2011). These three constructs need for closure, providing the cognitive anchor that keeps religious commitment in place, social relationships, providing the exposure, and sensation seeking, supplying the emotional drive, may actually work in concert.

Despite the theoretical promise, empirical work combining these factors remains scarce. Existing studies tend to examine these constructs separately, focusing on sensation seeking in relation to risk and religiosity (Hatam et al., 2017), social association in the context of learning and prison religion (Clear et

al., 2000), or need for closure in relation to ideological rigidity and dogmatism (Roets & Van Hiel, 2011). The present study seeks to fill that gap by examining whether sensation seeking, deviant associations, and need for cognitive closure jointly predict religious passion.

Conceptual Model

Hypothesis

H1: Sensation seeking, deviant association, and need for closure lead to passion for religion.

H2: There is a significant correlation among sensation seeking, deviant association, need for closure, and passion for religion.

Method

Participants

The population of this study, where we collected data from different locations and different people, i.e, from prisoners, drug addicts and college students. A total of 354 individuals were involved in the study, and data were collected from four different places. The data collected from people, of which prisoners were 33.1% (n=117), drug addicts were 13.8% (n=49), students were 24.9% (n=88), and online participants were 28.2% (n=100). Out of all the participants, 79.7% (n=282) were males and 20.3% (n=72) were females. Based on education, 23.4% (n=83) were bachelor's

students, 70.6% (n=250) had done FSc, 5.1% (n=18) had done Matric, and 0.8% (n=3) were master's students. Of the participants, 34.7% (n=123) were married and 65.3% (n=231) were unmarried. From the participants, 105 individuals were prisoners, and only 2.5% (n=9) participants mentioned that they had some type of mental illness. The treatment of participants, their anonymity, the acquisition of their free and informed consent, and the maintenance of complete confidentiality were all conducted following ethical principles. The purposive sampling method was used in the study to collect data.

Deviant Association

Deviant association was assessed with the help of an 8-item scale developed by Moyano (2011), the deviant association scale. To check the people's association with deviant groups. The scale counted on these substances on a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from (1=Not agree at all, 7=very strongly agree). The value of Cronbach's alpha was .78.

Measurement Instruments

Sensation Seeking

Sensation seeking was measured with the help of a 6-item sensation seeking scale established by Zuckerman et al. (1964). The respondent needs to score on a Likert format with (1=not agree at all, 7=very strongly agree). The Cronbach alpha was .58.

Need for Closure

The Need for closure was assessed with the use of a 5-item short version of the Need for Closure Scale established by Roets & Van Hiel (2011). Respondent needed to answer on a 6-point Likert passion scale ranging from (1=not agree at all, 7=very strongly agree). The higher scores mean an extreme need for safe answers and little tolerance for hesitation. The value of Cronbach's alpha was satisfactory.

Passion for Religion

The religious passion for religion was measured with the 16-item passion scale established by Vallerand et al. (2003). It is used to measure two magnitudes: 8 items assess harmonious passion, and 8 items assess obsessive passion. Participants must answer on a 6-point Likert scale, which ranges from (1=not agree at all, 7=very strongly agree). The value of Cronbach's alpha for harmonious passion was .84, and for obsessive passion it was .79.

Procedure

In the initial stage, permission was taken from the authorities of the concerned organization or institution. The purposive sampling technique was used to approach students, prisoners and drug addicts in the second step. In the third step, individuals were provided with a comprehensive explanation,

Study's Result

emphasizing the voluntary role of their participation and clarifying that no academic credit would be granted as an incentive for participating in the research survey. Questionnaires were distributed among participants, which took approximately 15 to 20 minutes to complete. Following the conclusion of data collection, all questionnaire responses were collected, and the data were input into data management software, namely SPSS and subsequently subjected to analysis.

Analytic Approach

SPSS and AMOS were used to conduct statistical studies. Descriptive statistics were computed based on the sample's characteristics. Regression analyses were used to determine whether sensation seeking, deviant association, and need for closure significantly predicted passion for religion. For this study, the reliability of scales according to Cronbach's alpha was satisfactory.

Ethical approval

Informed consent was taken from the participants, and the participants were informed about the purpose of the current research. No such committee exists in our institute; therefore, all the ethical procedures were taken into examination during the entire process.

Table 1. Regression Analysis between Sensation seeking, deviant association, need for closure and Passion for religion.

Variables	B	95%CI		SE B	β	R^2	ΔR^2
		LB	UB				
Constant	49.56	[38.88	60.24]	5.41		.414	.414***
Sensation Seeking	1.07***	[.794	1.35]	.141	.431***		
Deviant Association	-.47***	[-.63	-.32]	.079	-.34***		
Need for Closure	.533***	[.248	.817]	.144	.206***		

Note. CI = Confidence Interval *** $P < .001$.

Table 1 examined the influence of sensation seeking, deviant association, and need for closure on passion

for religion. The overall model was significant with $R^2 = .414$, indicating that about 41.4% of the variance in passion for religion is explained by these predictors. Sensation seeking emerged as a strong positive predictor ($B = 1.07, \beta = .431, p < .001$), showing that individuals with higher sensation-seeking tendencies are significantly more likely to report greater passion for religion. In contrast, deviant association was a negative predictor ($B = -0.47, \beta = -.34, p < .001$), suggesting that higher involvement in deviant

associations is related to a lower level of passion for religion. On the other hand, need for closure ($\beta = .206$) also showed a significant effect, indicating that it also contributes meaningfully to explaining passion for religion. Overall, sensation seeking was the strongest positive predictor ($\beta = .431$), while deviant association was a negative predictor ($\beta = -.34$) of passion for religion.

Table 2 - Evaluation Table of Correlation among Variables of the study model (N=354)

Variables	Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5
Sensation Seeking	21.26	5.18	-	-	-	-	-
Deviant Association	33.14	9.46	-.206**	-	-	-	-
Need for Closure	22.01	4.98	.026	-.009	-	-	-
Passion for Religion	68.23	12.95	.507**	-.435**	.223**	-	-

$p < .001$ **. Correlation is significant at the level of 0.01 (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that sensation seeking ($M = 21.26, SD = 5.18$) has a strong positive correlation with passion for religion ($r = .507, p < .01$), indicating that individuals who score higher on sensation seeking also report higher levels of religious passion. Deviant association ($M = 33.14, SD = 9.46$) was negatively associated with passion for religion ($r = -.435, p < .01$), suggesting that those with stronger peer influences demonstrated lower levels of religious passion. Need for closure was also positively associated with passion for religion, $r(223, p < .001)$, showing that individuals with a higher preference for certainty and structure were more likely to report strong passion for religion. Additionally, sensation seeking was negatively correlated with deviant association, $r(-.206, p < .01)$, while no significant correlations were found between sensation seeking and need for closure or between deviant association and need for closure. Collectively, these findings indicate that passion for religion is most strongly influenced by sensation seeking and deviant

association, with need for closure playing a smaller but significant role.

General Discussion

The present study investigated the impact of sensation seeking, deviant association, and need for closure on passion for religion among a diverse sample consisting of students, prisoners, drug addicts, and online participants. The findings demonstrated that whereas deviant association predicted religious passion negatively, sensation seeking and the need for closure both predicted it favorably. This helps us understand how social factors and individual characteristics affect religious passion. Sensation seeking and passion for religion are strongly positively correlated, which implies that religion can truly be a way for many people to satisfy their desire for excitement and stimulation.

Sensation seekers are drawn to novel, intense, and emotionally charged encounters, according to a prior

study (Zuckerman, 2007). That type of stimulation is frequently offered by religious rituals, spiritual practices, and collective worship, which give people experiences that are emotionally captivating and even thrilling (Saroglou, 2011).

The need for closure has also been shown to be a significant predictor of religious passion. Those with high scores on this characteristic typically favor answers that are clear, orderly, and certain (Kruglanski & Webster, 1996). Religion appears to satisfy that desire by providing unambiguous guidance and lowering uncertainty through its structured doctrines and moral laws. According to prior research, those who have a strong need for closure are more likely to turn to religion because it gives them stability and helps them deal with ambiguity when making decisions (Saroglou, 2002; Neuberg et al., 2010). In this way, religion serves as a cognitive framework that gives people a sense of stability in the face of uncertainty.

Conversely, deviant association was a poor predictor of passion for religion. This demonstrates the importance of social factors in determining religious participation. People can be exposed to different ideals and worldviews that go against traditional religious norms by hanging around with deviant peers. This is consistent with the social learning theory, which contends that interacting with deviant groups frequently results in the acquisition of deviant attitudes and behaviors (Akers, 2009).

Taken together, these results imply that passion for religion encompasses more than just internal spirituality. Rather, it is influenced by social context as well as psychological demands. While deviant associations can draw people away by promoting conflicting values, those with a strong need for closure may utilize religion for structure and certainty, and sensation seekers may lean toward it because it stimulates them. Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of research demonstrating how religion satisfies social and personal needs and offers new perspectives on the causes of passion for religion.

Conclusion

The present research places of interest the mutual effect of psychological characters and social settings in influencing passion for religion. Results specify that sensation seeking and need for closure absolutely

predict religious passion, proposing that religion can work as both a basis of inspiration and an agenda for mental conviction. Equally, deviant associations negatively affect religious passion, highlighting the role of social networks in determining pledge to religious standards. By incorporating these predictors, the study progresses by considering how personal characteristics and social stimuli cooperate to raise or reduce religious rendezvous. These understandings may inform future spiritual research, involvement plans, and community-based plans intended to improve positive religious participation and justify the effects of deviant associations.

REFERENCES

- Akers, R. L. (1990). Rational choice, deterrence, and social learning theory in criminology: The path not taken. *The Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology*, 81(3), 653–676. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1143850>
- Akers, R. L. (1998). *Social learning and social structure: A general theory of crime and deviance*. Northeastern University Press.
- Akers, R. L. (1998). *Social learning and social structure: A general theory of crime and deviance*. Northeastern University Press.
- Akers, R. L. (2000). *Criminological theories: Introduction, evaluation, and applications* (3rd ed.). Roxbury Publishing Company.
- Akers, R. L. (2017). *Social learning and social structure: A general theory of crime and deviance*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315130620>
- Akers, R. L., & Jennings, W. G. (2016). Social learning theory. In A. R. Piquero (Ed.), *The handbook of criminological theory* (pp. 230–240). Wiley Blackwell. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118517384.ch12>
- Akers, R. L., Sellers, C. S., & Jennings, W. G. (2016). *Criminological theories: Introduction, evaluation, and applications* (7th ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Bandura, A. (1971). *Social learning theory*. General Learning Press.
- Bandura, A. (1977). *Social learning theory*. Prentice-Hall.

- Bower, G. H., & Hilgard, E. R. (1981). *Theories of learning* (5th ed.). Prentice-Hall.
- Brandt, M. J., Reyna, C., Chambers, J. R., Crawford, J. T., & Wetherell, G. (2014). The ideological-conflict hypothesis: Intolerance among both liberals and conservatives. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 23(1), 27-34.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721413510932>
- Burgess, R. L., & Akers, R. L. (1966). A differential association-reinforcement theory of criminal behavior. *Social Problems*, 14(2), 128-147.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/799147>
- Centola, D. (2018). *How behavior spreads: The science of complex contagions*. Princeton University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400890055>
- Clear, T. R., & Sumter, M. T. (2002). Prisoners, prison, and religion: Religion and adjustment to prison. *Journal of Offender Rehabilitation*, 35(3-4), 125-156.
[https://doi.org/10.1300/J076v35n03_07]
(https://doi.org/10.1300/J076v35n03_07)
- Clear, T. R., Hardyman, P., Stout, B., Lucken, K., & Dammer, H. R. (2000). The value of religion in prison: An inmate perspective. *Journal of Contemporary Criminal Justice*, 16(1), 53-74.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1043986200016001004>
- Hatam, S., Baranovich, D.-L., & Shahbazi-Fard, M. (2017). Sensation seeking and religious orientation: Correlation study. *European Psychiatry*, 41(S1), S724.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eurpsy.2017.01.1198>
- Hedström, P. (1998). Rational imitation. In P. Hedström & R. Swedberg (Eds.), *Social mechanisms: An analytical approach to social theory* (pp. 306-327). Cambridge University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511663901.011>
- Kruglanski, A. W., & Webster, D. M. (1996). Motivated closing of the mind: "Seizing" and "freezing." *Psychological Review*, 103(2), 263-283. [<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.103.2.263>]
- Neuberg, S. L., Schimel, J., & Williams, K. D. (2010). Terror management theory and religion. In P. McNamara & W. Wildman (Eds.), *Science and the world's religions* (pp. 25-45). ABC-CLIO.
- Oliver, P., & Marwell, G. (2002). Recent developments in critical mass theory. In J. Berger & M. Zelditch Jr. (Eds.), *New directions in contemporary sociological theory* (pp. 172-193). Rowman & Littlefield.
- Pargament, K. I. (1997). *The psychology of religion and coping: Theory, research, practice*. Guilford Press.
- Roets, A., & Van Hiel, A. (2011). Item selection and validation of a brief, 15-item version of the Need for Closure Scale. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 50(1), 90-94.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2010.09.004>
- Saroglou, V. (2002). Religion and the five factors of personality: A meta-analytic review. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 32(1), 15-25. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869\(00\)00233-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0191-8869(00)00233-6)
- Saroglou, V. (2011). Believing, bonding, behaving, and belonging: The big four religious dimensions and cultural variation. *Journal of Cross-Cultural Psychology*, 42(8), 1320-1340.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0022022111412267>
- Zinnbauer, B. J., & Pargament, K. I. (2005). Religiousness and spirituality. In R. F. Paloutzian & C. L. Park (Eds.), *Handbook of the psychology of religion and spirituality* (pp. 21-42). Guilford Press.
- Zuckerman, M. (1994). *Behavioral expressions and biosocial bases of sensation seeking*. Cambridge University Press